

COREnect Provisioning Ecosystem: The COREnect Community

COREnect Use-Case Ecosystem: Users of the COREnect Technologies

Policy Makers
CEPT, EC, ECC, ECC PT1, ITU, ITU-R WP5D; national regulators e.g. OFCOM; vertical policy makers e.g. healthcare, energy, transport, media (EBU), etc.

Financing Bodies
EC (e.g. ERDF, EAFRD for agriculture), EIB, WHO (health), EMFF (maritime), National, Regional and Local Public Authorities and Agencies in charge of supporting vertical sectors; private investors in vertical sectors

Standardisation organisations
those that are relevant to vertical sectors for adopting COREnect technologies

Open Source organisations
those that are relevant to vertical sectors for adopting COREnect technologies

Initiatives

Projects

Mobility: ERTRAC, ERRAC, 5G-ACIA, 5GAA, ERTICO, EATA, CCAM, UIC, ACEA, IRU, Mobility.E Lighthouse, EGVA, EGCI; **Media:** NEM, EBU
Health and wellbeing: ECHalliance, PCHalliance, 5G Health Association, WHO, 5GtoGo, European Association for logistics and transport in Healthcare, EU4Health
Energy: EUTC, EDSO, FEDARENE, ETIP
Industry/Manufacturing: 5GACIA, IIC, EFFRA
Maritime: IALA
Manufacture: Textile ETP.
Agriculture: European Environment Agency

Mobility: 5GENESIS, 5G VINNI, 5GIDRONES, 5GROWTH, 5GHEART, 5G TOURS, 5G VICTORI, 5GCroCo - 5G-CARMEN - 5G-MOBIX, 5GMED - 5G-Blueprint - 5G-Routes, 5GMETA, 5G-ROUTES. AutoDrive, SECREDAS, BRAVE, interACT, TrustVehicle, New Control, InsecTT, PRYSTINE, A14CSM, ADACORSA.
Media: 5GENESIS, 5G EVE, 5GIDRONES, 5G SOLUTIONS, 5G TOURS, 5GVICTORI, 5G-RECORDS. Media4U, Starts4media, 5G-VICTORI
Manufacturing: 5G SMART
Health and wellbeing: 5G EVE, 5G HEART, 5G TOURS, 5G research for rural health care, 5GeHealthSax, Health5G, MOMENTUM
Energy: 5G EVE, 5G VINNI, 5G GROWTH, 5G SOLUTIONS, 5G VICTORI
Digital Society: GAIA-X
Logistics: 5GLOGINNOV
Vertical trials: 5G-EPICENTRE (security/PPDR), 5GMediaHub(media), 5G-INDUCE (industry 4.0), 5G-IANA, 5G GROCO, 5G Carmen, 5G Mobix (automotive), 5GROWTH

Vertical device vendors
Intermediary "modem vendors" / integrators
IoT specialised end device vendors
Specialised intermediaries
Industrial Applications – connected smart fab

Mobility: automotive, rail, maritime, shared service provider,
Infrastructure: telecom, road transport monitoring, etc..
Media: studios, broadcasters, content providers, etc.
Health and wellbeing: pharmaceutical companies, emergency services, insurance companies, etc.
Digital industry: factories of the future, manufacturing, logistics, etc.
Energy: power companies, utilities, smart grid operators, etc.
Public safety: police, rescue and fire departments, ambulance, etc.
Digital Society: smart cities, tourism, consumers, etc.

* Large companies, SMEs and research institutions are stakeholders of this category and in all its sub-groups